

Local Government in Poland

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Structure of Local Government

4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Poland: An Introduction

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The number of local government units in Poland is relatively stable. As far as the number of *gminas* [communes, municipalities] is concerned, there were 2,383 at the time of the restoration of local government in 1990. Currently, there are 2,477 of them. This means an increase in the number of *gminas* by 3.9 per cent. Between 1990 and 2018, the number of *gminas* with less than 2,000 inhabitants increased from 15 to 40, while the number of *gminas* with less than 5,000 inhabitants increased from 654 to 794⁸⁷. The number of cities with *powiat* rights remains unchanged and currently stands at 66.

The number of *powiats* [counties], that were established in 1999 was 308, currently there are 314. The structure of voivodeships (16 units) did not change.

However, this does not mean that the problem of the territorial structure in Poland does not provoke disputes and political discussion. On the one hand, local communities are active and take initiatives to establish separate smaller territorial units. On the other hand, the central government, which has authority to introduce changes in the territorial structure of the country, proposes solutions aimed at consolidating small *gminas* and *powiats*. Moreover, a discussion is taking place among experts about dysfunctions in the territorial division and the desirable changes. The discussion about metropolitanization processes is especially important. It entails the determination of the development strategy for Poland (polarization-diffusion model versus sustainable development model)⁸⁸.

Thus, territorial units in Poland have not been consolidated, which has been a dominant trend in the last few decades in European countries (e.g. Germany, Sweden, Switzerland, Denmark, the Netherlands).

The numerous causes for the process opposite to consolidation, i.e. fragmentation of the *gmina* structure in Poland, include inter alia:

- the establishment of new *gminas* was a manifestation of grassroots social movements in the process of democratization and restoration of self-government after 1990. Local government in localities was often considered an important value;

⁸⁷ Katarzyna Ciesielska, Ewa Kacperczyk, Krystyna Korczak-Żydaczewska and Mirosława Zagrodzka, 'Demographic Yearbook of Poland' (Statistics Poland 2019) <<https://stat.gov.pl/obszary-tematyczne/ludnosc/ludnosc/powierzchnia-i-ludnosc-w-przekroju-terytorialnym-w-2019-roku,7,16.html>> accessed 22 November 2019.

⁸⁸ Andżelika Mirska, 'Probleme der Metropolitanisierung in Polen in Hinblick auf die territoriale Struktur des Landes' in Europäisches Zentrum für Föderalismus-Forschung Tübingen EZFF (ed), *Jahrbuch des Föderalismus 2013: Föderalismus, Subsidiarität und Regionen in Europa* (Nomos 2013).

- the lack of statutory provisions on the criteria for the establishment of new *gminas* resulted in spontaneous and uncontrolled division.

It was only in 2015 that a legal provision was introduced to counteract the fragmentation of the territorial structure in Poland. The criterion of *gmina* revenue and population size was adopted.

The above provision prohibits the establishment of *gminas* in which:

- the revenue would be lower than the lowest tax revenues per capita provided for individual *gminas* in the Act of 13 November 2003 on Revenue of Local Government Units;
- the population of the newly established *gmina* would be lower than that in the *gmina* with the smallest population in Poland.⁸⁹

On the other hand, incentives for voluntary mergers of *gminas* and *powiats* are offered. They include financial incentives which were first introduced in Poland in 2003. *Gmina* or *powiat* established as a result of voluntary consolidation is provided with additional funds from the state budget for 5 years (increased share in PIT revenues for a new *gmina* or *powiat*).⁹⁰ Even so, there had not been a single consolidation of territorial units in Poland until 2015.⁹¹ For this reason, the financial incentive was increased in 2015. The first voluntary merger took place in 2015. Two territorial units were consolidated: the city with *powiat* rights (Zielona Góra) was merged with the surrounding rural *gmina* (under the same name: Zielona Góra). The initiative was undertaken by the city which conducted an intensive promotional campaign for the merger. The authorities of the rural *gmina* were rather reluctant and sceptical. Eventually, in a local referendum, which took place only in the rural *gmina*, 53.4 per cent of the inhabitants voted in favor of the merger. Accordingly, the Polish government decided to merge the two *gminas*. As a result, Zielona Góra (city with *powiat* rights) increased its area from 58.34 sq m to 278.79 sq m, becoming the sixth largest city in Poland. The population has increased by about 20,000 and is now 140,000 inhabitants.

The financial incentives are crucial in joining local government units on the example of Zielona Góra issue. What is more, residents of the village were allowed by the authorities of Zielona Góra to decide (during the village meetings) about the allocation of additional funds from the state budget on the investments. As announced by the Mayor of Zielona Góra, the money was divided among the village councils in proportion to the number of individual villages' residents. The infrastructure investment extending and the areas increase intended for investment were the most expected benefits during the information campaign for the connection of the City of

⁸⁹ Art 4(d) of the Act of 8 March 1990 on *Gmina* Self-Government.

⁹⁰ Art 41 of the Act of 13 November 2003 on the Revenues of Local Government Units.

⁹¹ The response of the Ministry of Administration and Digitization to parliamentary question no 24063 on the consequences of administrative reform, <<http://www.sejm.gov.pl/sejm7.nsf/InterpelacjaTresc.xsp?key=0F92DD9D> > accessed 22 November 2019.

Zielona Góra and the rural Commune of Zielona Góra. Conversely, the local taxes raise and the cost of living increases for rural areas residents could be the main threats to the rural communities.⁹²

All adjustments to the territorial structure of *gminas*, *powiats* and voivodships are made by the central government in Poland. It is mandatory for the government to consult the local authorities affected by these changes. Both representative bodies and residents are consulted (a local referendum may be carried out). However, the outcome of the consultations is not binding on the government. The residents also have the right to take the initiative to establish, merge, divide and liquidate a *gmina* and establish the borders of the territorial unit. It is implemented in the form of a local referendum.

As regard the aforementioned issue of consolidation of territorial units, the above example of Zielona Góra draws attention to a wider problem of territorial structure in Poland, namely the so-called ‘bagel’-*gminas* [*gminy obwarzankowe*] (Figure below). This means that in the vicinity of a rural *gmina* there is a separate city (urban *gmina* or city with *powiat* rights) – often with the same name. As there is no administrative center in a rural *gmina*, the authorities and administration of that rural *gmina* are based in a neighboring city (which is a separate *gmina* with its own authorities and administration). It is often the case that the rural and municipal authorities are based in the same building.

Figure 9: Examples of the shape of ‘bagel’-*gminas*.⁹³

In Poland there are 144 urban *gminas* (and 14 cities with *powiat* rights) surrounded by rural *gminas* – ‘bagels’. According to some experts, a systemic solution is needed – i.e. a merger of

⁹² Piotr Dubicki and Piotr Kułyk, ‘Proces integracji miasta z gminą wiejską. Przykład Zielonej Góry. The Process of Urban-Rural Integration. Using the Example of Zielona góra’ (2018) 32 *Studia Miejskie* 113 <http://www.studiamiejskie.uni.opole.pl/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/S_Miejskie_32_2018-Dubicki.pdf>.

⁹³ Source: own elaboration based on Association of Volunteer Firefighting Brigades, ‘Lista stron OSP’ (*Związek Ochotniczych Straży Pożarnych RP*, 2008) <https://www.osp.org.pl/hosting/katalog.php?id_w=16&id_p=309&id_g=2281> accessed 2 November 2019.

all ‘bagel’-*gminas* with cities. The authorities of individual cities and the Association of Polish Cities (*Związek Miast Polskich*) also propose such a solution.⁹⁴ They claim that the inhabitants move from the city to the suburbs, i.e. to the area of the rural *gmina* (where they also pay PIT which contributes towards the budget of the rural *gmina*), and work in the city and use the local infrastructure (the free-rider problem). It is also argued that cities need land for urban investments. However, the ‘bagel’-*gminas* are reluctant to hold negotiations about consolidation with the city and are concerned about a loss of identity, independence and, of course, financial independence. It is argued that the indebted cities want to repair their finances through a merger with a rural *gminas* (bonus from the central budget). The 2013 report of the Minister of Administration and Digitization states that the government does not plan systemic solutions and top-down liquidation of all the ‘bagel’ *gminas* but only expects voluntary mergers.⁹⁵

In recent years, the conflict between urban and rural *gminas* in Poland has been aggravating. Cities are attempting to take over some of the rural areas (officially: adjustment of borders between territorial units). The parties to the conflict are represented by local government organizations: the Association of Rural Communes (*Związek Gmin Wiejskich*) and Association of Polish Cities. Both parties present conflicting demands and they seek to win over the Polish government. Rural *gminas* demand a guarantee of inviolability of their borders,⁹⁶ while cities postulate that the government should issue permits to increase their area at the expense of neighboring *gminas*, as they need land for investments.⁹⁷ In each case, the government decides on the adjustment of the borders between the territorial units – considering the requests of the cities to take over a part of the area of the neighboring *gmina*.

Since the territorial reform of 1999, metropolitan areas have not been regulated. The government proposed various top-down solutions – however, none of them eventually was adopted. The dispute concerned, among other things, the question of which cities in Poland

⁹⁴ Tomasz Żółciak, ‘Cicha wojna na linii gminy - miasta o zmiany granic [Silent War Between Rural Gminas and Cities for Changes of Borders]’ (*GazetaPrawna.pl*, 31 January 2018) <<https://serwisy.gazetaprawna.pl/samorząd/artykuly/1101214,wojna-na-linii-gminy-miasta-o-zmiany-granic.html>> accessed 22 November 2019.

⁹⁵ Ministry of Administration and Digitization, ‘Assessment of the Situation of Local Governments’ (2013) <<http://eregion.wzp.pl/sites/default/files/ocena-sytuacji-samorządow-lokalnych.pdf> > accessed 1 December 2019.

⁹⁶ Position of the 32nd General Assembly of the Association of Rural Communes of the Republic of Poland of 19 June 2018 on amendments to the law on the division and change of *gminas*’ borders, <http://www.zgwrp.pl/attachments/article/1352/XXXIIIZO_stanowisko_granice.pdf> accessed 1 December 2019. Katarzyna Kubicka-Żac, ‘Gminy wiejskie chcą lepszej ochrony swych granic [Rural Gminas Demand Better Protection of their Borders]’ (*Prawo.pl*, 27 April 2019) <<https://www.prawo.pl/samorząd/gminy-wiejskie-chca-lepszej-ochrony-swych-granic,402541.html>> accessed 1 December 2019.

⁹⁷ Aneta Kaczmarek, ‘Zmiany granic gmin. „Zbyt łatwo silniejszy zabiera ziemię słabszemu” [Changes in the gminas’ Borders. “Too Easily the Stronger Takes the Land from the Weaker”]’ (*Portal Samorządowy*, 7 November 2019) <<https://www.portalsamorządowy.pl/prawo-i-finanse/zmiany-granic-gmin-zbyt-latwo-silniejszy-zabiera-ziemie-slabszemu,134527.html>> accessed 30 November 2019.

can be considered as ‘metropolises’. Government documents from 2011 referred to 10 metropolitan areas, identified on the basis of a number of criteria, including the population over 30 000.⁹⁸ However, no new territorial units have been created. The progress was made in 2017, when the first metropolitan territorial unit in Poland was established. Under an act, the Upper Silesian and Zagłębie Metropolis [*Górnośląsko-Zagłębiowska Metropolia*], i.e. the metropolitan union for the metropolitan area of the Upper Silesian conurbation, was established. To date, no other metropolitan union has been established by a top-down decision.

For years, however, very large cities with their surrounding *gminas* and *powiats* have been establishing grassroots associations and arrangements to jointly carry out tasks in functional areas (e.g. a joint metropolitan ticket for public transport).

Examples of voluntary cooperation in the functional areas of the largest cities in Poland include:

- Gdańsk-Gdynia-Sopot Metropolitan Area⁹⁹ (2011), an association of 57 local governments, an area of 5.500 sq km with 1.5 million inhabitants;
- Metropolis of Poznań¹⁰⁰ (2007), an association of 23 local governments, 3,000 sq km, 1 million inhabitants.

However, this was not a common practice in large Polish cities. One method of encouraging or even forcing cooperation between large cities and their functional areas involved a financial incentive from the European Regional Development Fund and the European Social Fund. It involves an instrument implemented in Poland to support cities, namely the Integrated Territorial Investment (ITI). Large cities and surrounding *gminas*, in order to cooperate under the ITI model, establish a partnership (e.g. an association or an inter-*gmina* union) or enter into an agreement and prepare a joint ITI strategy. It should include objectives and projects to be implemented.

Thus, the largest cities were ‘forced’ to cooperate in exchange for additional funding. This resulted in the cooperation between local governments, e.g.

- Cracow Metropolis¹⁰¹ (2014), 15 local governments, 1.2 million inhabitants, 1,275 sq m;
- Warsaw Functional Area¹⁰² (2014), Warsaw and 39 *gminas* surrounding Warsaw, 2.7 million inhabitants, area of 2,932 sq km.

⁹⁸ Ministry of Regional Development, ‘Concept of the Country’s Spatial Development 2030’ (2011) 167 <http://www.wzs.wzp.pl/sites/default/files/files/19683/89272000_1412985316_Koncepcja_Przestrzennego_Zagospodarowania_Kraju_2030.pdf> accessed 30 November 2019.

⁹⁹ Website of the Gdańsk-Gdynia-Sopot Metropolitan Area, <<http://en.metropoliagdansk.pl/>>.

¹⁰⁰ Website of the Metropolis of Poznań <<http://metropoliapoznan.pl/strona,27,dzialalnosc.html>>.

¹⁰¹ Website of the Cracow Metropolis <<http://metropoliakrakowska.pl/>>.

¹⁰² Website of the Warsaw Functional Area <<https://omw.um.warszawa.pl/>>.

Moreover, the EU funds allow the implementation of cross-border cooperation programs. These programs are open to participation, alongside other entities, of cross-border local governments from Poland and neighboring countries. Programs carried out currently (2014-2020): 'Poland-Slovakia', 'Poland-Czech Republic', 'Poland-Saxony', 'Poland-Brandenburg', 'Poland-Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania-Brandenburg', 'Poland-Lithuania', 'Poland-Belarus-Ukraine', 'Poland-Russia', 'South Baltic' (Denmark, Lithuania, Germany, Poland and Sweden), 'Baltic Sea Region' (Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Lithuania, Latvia, Estonia, selected regions of North-East Germany, non-EU countries): Norway, Belarus, Russia).¹⁰³

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Kaczmarek T, 'Functional Urban Areas as the Focus of Development Policy in Poland' (2015) 29 *Rozwój Regionalny i Polityka Regionalna* 9 <http://obserwatorium.miasta.pl/wp-content/uploads/2016/10/RR29_009-019.pdf>

Swianiewicz P, 'If Territorial Fragmentation is a Problem, is Amalgamation a Solution? An East European Perspective' (2010) 36 *Local Government Studies* 183 <<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/03003930903560547>>

Mirska A, 'State policy on the formation and modernisation of Polish territorial structure' in Europäisches Zentrum für Föderalismus-Forschung Tübingen EZFF (ed), *Jahrbuch des Föderalismus 2018: Föderalismus, Subsidiarität und Regionen in Europa* (Nomos 2018)

¹⁰³ Ministry of Development Funds and Regional Policy, 'Programy Europejskiej Współpracy Terytorialnej i Europejskiego Instrumentu Sąsiedztwa' (undated) <<http://www.ewt.gov.pl/strony/o-programach/przeczytaj-o-programach/>> accessed 1 December 2019.

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